

Energy Management in Lithium-Ion Battery and Supercapacitor Hybrid Systems: Techniques and Approaches

¹Ameer Hamza ,

⁴Mohammed Najeeb Ahmed Abdualjaleel Abdullallah

¹*Institute of Physics, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan*

²*Institute of Physics, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan*

³*Department of Civil Engineering, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan*

⁴*School of Economics, Wuban University of Technology, Wuban, China*

Abstract

The lithium-ion battery/supercapacitor hybrid energy storage system has become the most widely used hybrid energy storage system due to its excellent performance, low cost, and strong versatility. Energy management technology is one of the core technologies in hybrid energy storage systems and remains a significant research focus. To systematically review the energy management methods for hybrid energy storage systems, this article first introduces the topology, energy management architecture, and power allocation control of lithium-ion battery/supercapacitor hybrid systems. Next, the article categorizes existing energy management methods for hybrid energy storage systems into five main types: experience-based, optimization-based, operating condition pattern recognition-based, and machine learning-based. A detailed comparative analysis is provided, with a focus on evaluating the effectiveness of various energy management methods under both regular and random operating conditions. The robustness and computational complexity of each method are also discussed. Finally, the article summarizes current energy management methods and outlines future research directions and development trends in this field. The comprehensive analysis suggests that improving the prediction accuracy of future operating conditions for random loads, establishing more precise hybrid energy storage system models, and enhancing the real-time performance of energy management methods through cloud collaboration will be key areas of focus for future research in hybrid energy storage systems.

Keywords: *hybrid energy storage system, supercapacitor, Lithium-ion battery, energy management.*

Introduction

Energy storage technology, as a key supporting technology in the new energy industry (Baker, 2008; Hong, 2023), is commonly used for peak shaving and valley filling in the power grid, overcoming the intermittency of renewable energy generation, improving power quality, and providing power for electric vehicles (Shoukat, 2022), light rail trains, ships, and other transportation tools. With the development of energy storage technology (Niaz, 2023), lithium-ion batteries (LIB) have become the most widely used energy storage device in the new energy industry due to their higher energy density, better power performance, extremely low self-discharge rate, and lower cost (Shafiei, 2025). However, energy storage

Article History:

Received: 10.05.2025

Revised: 3.06.2025

Accepted: 5.06.2025

Published: 09.06.2025

Citation: Hamza, A., Javid, M.A., Hayyat, S., & Abdullallah, M.N.A.A. (2025). Energy Management in Lithium-Ion Battery and Supercapacitor Hybrid Systems: Techniques and Approaches. *European Journal of Science and Modern Technologies*, 1(1), 71-80. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1\(1\).05](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1(1).05)

© The Author(s) 2025. Published by [AMO Publisher](#). This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

systems composed solely of LIBs still have many shortcomings. For example, their performance deteriorates significantly at low temperatures, and their lifespan rapidly decreases. High-rate pulse discharge and fluctuating power throughput demands also lead to the rapid aging of LIB-based energy storage systems (Cheng, 2020). Additionally, because LIBs do not excel in power performance, applications requiring high power and low energy demand, or those with long lifespan requirements, require the stacking of excessive battery cells. This results in large system volume and weight, along with high battery acquisition, operation, and management costs (Ren, 2015).

Therefore, improving the operating conditions of LIBs and slowing down their capacity degradation has become a core issue in energy storage technology research. Combining two or more energy storage systems into a hybrid energy storage system (HESS) can take advantage of the strengths of each, effectively solving the issues of low temperatures, high-rate pulse discharge, and power fluctuations that affect the lifespan of LIB systems (Xiong, 2018). In HESS, power-type devices and energy-type devices can be flexibly configured based on application needs, avoiding the excessive stacking of battery cells and reducing the acquisition, operation, and management costs of the energy storage system. The performance parameters of current mainstream energy storage systems are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Performance Parameters of Mainstream Energy Storage Systems

Energy Storage Type	Power Density (W/kg)	Energy Density (Wh/kg)	Daily Discharge Rate (%)	Response Time (s)	Efficiency (%)	Calendar Life (years)	Cycle Life (times)
Compressed Air (Kouchachvili, 2018; Li, 2008)	—	30~60	0	40~70	20~40	—	—
Flywheel (Youfeng, 2025; Li, 2021)	400~1600	5~130	20~100	80~90	15~20	$10^4 \sim 10^7$	—
Supercapacitor (Wu, 2025; Manikandan, 2025)	3000~50000	5~20	2~40	85~98	5~12	$10^5 \sim 10^6$	500~2000
Lead-Acid Battery (Yanamandra, 2022)	20~200	30~50	0.1~1	78~85	5~10	1000~3000	500~2000
Nickel-Cadmium Battery (Petrovic, 2021)	250~450	130~250	0.1~0.3	80~90	1~5	1000~1200	1000~3000
Lithium-Ion Battery (Takyi-Aninakwa; Hasan, 2025)	100~120	100~150	0~1	70~90	5~30	1000~3000	$>10^4$
Flow Battery (Reber 2025)	30~60	30~50	0~1	20~66	5~30	$10^3 \sim 10^4$	$>10^4$
Fuel Cell (Abedin, 2025)	3000~5400/WL	500~3000	0.5~2	70~90	1~5	1000~1200	$>10^4$

Supercapacitors (SC) (Wang, 2025) are similar to LIBs in terms of volume, cost, working mode, and calendar life, but they complement LIBs well in terms of electrical performance, such as power density, energy density, self-discharge rate, and cycle life (Olabi, 2022). HESS consisting of LIB and SC has been widely used as a power source or power buffer system for various electric vehicles (Li, 2021), as well as for energy storage systems in power grids, wind farms, and photovoltaic power plants. Currently, research in academia on HESS is largely focused on HESS composed of LIB and SC.

Although the LIB/SC hybrid energy storage system has clear advantages over pure LIB energy storage systems, achieving the complementary advantages of LIB and SC requires scientifically and reasonably distributing the real-time power load between the two (Ahsan, 2022). This presents significant challenges in the design of energy management strategies for LIB/SC hybrid energy storage systems. Therefore, this paper starts with the topology of the LIB/SC hybrid energy storage system and briefly introduces the energy management system (EMS) framework of the LIB/SC hybrid energy storage system, along with the underlying power distribution control process. It then focuses on categorizing and comparing the energy management methods for LIB/SC hybrid energy storage systems. Finally, the paper summarizes the characteristics of existing energy management methods and looks ahead to the development trends and future research directions for energy management in LIB/SC hybrid energy storage systems.

Hybrid Energy Storage System

The choice of HESS topology determines whether power distribution control between subsystems can be achieved through the hybrid energy storage EMS (Roy, 2022). Based on whether power distribution between subsystems is controlled, the existing LIB/SC hybrid energy storage system topologies can be divided into two major categories: controlled topology and uncontrolled topology, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. HESS Topology Classification

In controlled HESS, the hybrid energy storage EMS controls power distribution between subsystems through the bidirectional DC/DC converter. According to the number and connection method of the bidirectional DC/DC converters, controlled HESS topologies can be divided into fully active topology and semi-active topology (Wang, 2018), as shown in Figures 2(a), (b), (c) and (d).

Figure 2(a) shows the topology of a fully active HESS (Shu, 2020). In this topology, the LIB and SC subsystems are connected to the DC bus through bidirectional DC/DC converters. In this case, the output power of each subsystem and the bus voltage are controllable, making it suitable for applications that require high stability of the bus voltage.

The primary function of controlled HESS topology is to achieve controlled current distribution between the LIB and SC subsystems. When the load power demand is fixed, a semi-active HESS structure controls the output power of the connected subsystem through a single bidirectional DC/DC converter, with the remaining power demand supplied by the other subsystem, thereby achieving controlled power distribution (Song, 2015). However, in this case, the bus voltage is no longer controllable.

Figures 2(b) and 2(c) show two different configurations of the semi-active HESS. When the SC subsystem is connected to the bus through a bidirectional DC/DC converter and the LIB subsystem is directly

connected to the bus, this is called the capacitor semi-active structure. Conversely, when the LIB subsystem is connected via the bidirectional DC/DC converter and the SC subsystem is directly connected to the bus, it is called the battery semi-active structure (Reddy, 2018). The semi-active structure, especially the capacitor semi-active structure, is currently the most commonly used HESS topology (Tong, 2025).

Figure 2. Hybrid Energy Storage System Topology Structure

Moreover, based on the above controlled HESS topologies, some researchers have proposed modifications to adapt to the specific operating conditions of HESS applications, such as adding controlled switches, adjusting connection methods, or using unidirectional DC/DC converters (Ramu, 2024). These modifications aim to reduce the weight of converters and improve energy efficiency according to the application scenarios, but their core function remains to achieve controlled power distribution between subsystems.

The core of HESS energy management is to scientifically and reasonably distribute the load power demand between the LIB and SC subsystems (Vanlalchhuanawmi, 2024). For HESS topologies, only controlled topologies can achieve controlled power distribution between subsystems. Therefore, the energy management methods described in this paper apply to active, semi-active, and other controlled HESS. Uncontrolled (passive) HESS cannot perform energy management.

Energy Management System Functional Architecture

The Hybrid Energy Storage EMS (Energy Management System) is the key to ensuring the economic and stable operation of HESS and fully leveraging the performance advantages of LIB and SC (Gopi, 2024). Its primary function is to collect, process, and analyze information such as temperature, bus, and subsystem voltages and currents, and based on this, make decisions and control the input/output power of each subsystem, ensuring that the real-time power demand of the load is met, in order to extend the life of HESS (Mallon, 2022), improve energy utilization efficiency (Ruan, 2017), and achieve stable, efficient, and economical operation of the system (Hu, 2020). In addition, the hybrid energy storage EMS must also incorporate the functions of a traditional Battery Management System (BMS), such as measurement, assessment, balancing, and protection (Kumaresan, 2024). The functional architecture of the Hybrid Energy Storage EMS is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Hybrid Energy Storage EMS Functional Architecture

It can be seen that, for HESS with controllable subsystem power output, the main function of its EMS is to perform power distribution control based on the collection of necessary data, in order to achieve efficient, economical, and long-lifetime operation of the HESS. Measurement, assessment, balancing, and protection functions, typical of traditional BMS, are carried out by the subsystem BMS. When the subsystem power output is uncontrollable, the hybrid energy storage EMS functional architecture no longer includes the power distribution control section (i.e., the dashed box and dashed arrow section in Figure 3). At this point, the hybrid energy storage EMS essentially becomes a modular BMS (Shen, 2025).

Due to the scope of this topic, this paper will not discuss the relevant management methods for such BMS systems.

The main control unit of the hybrid energy storage EMS relies on the energy management algorithm running on it to provide power distribution reference values to the lower-level controllers. Then, through the lower-level controller, power distribution between subsystems in the controlled HESS topology is achieved via the control of the DC/DC converter. For semi-active HESS, the lower-level control only involves power distribution control between subsystems; for active HESS, the bus voltage must also be controlled (Jiang, 2025). Since the lower-level control issue of the semi-active topology is a subset of the lower-level control issue of the active topology, the following discussion on lower-level control will focus only on active HESS as an example. Figure 4 shows the general process of power distribution control in an active HESS.

Figure 4. General Process of Active HESS Power Allocation Control

In this process, the energy management algorithm runs in the hybrid energy storage EMS main control unit, which real-time receives load power demand and data such as voltage, current, temperature, and SOC from the LIB and SC subsystems, which are used as inputs for the energy management algorithm. Based on the aforementioned input data, the EMS main control unit, relying on the energy management algorithm, provides the lower-level controller with the bus voltage reference value as well as the output current reference value for any subsystem (the output current reference value of the other subsystem can be calculated by the control algorithm during bus voltage control). Then, the power distribution control algorithm in the lower-level controller takes these reference values and the required feedback data as inputs. The algorithm uses the duty cycles of the power electronic switches in the DC/DC converter, based on pulse width modulation (PWM), as the control quantity to achieve the lower-level feedback control of the HESS power distribution.

Future Research Outlook

For HESS aimed at random loads, particularly those for highly random loads represented by electric vehicles, developing an energy management method that is efficient, robust, and has low computational complexity is currently and will continue to be the main goal of HESS research for a considerable period. To achieve this goal, there are still three key issues that need to be addressed.

1. For random loads, the less uncertainty there is in the prediction of future operating conditions, the more likely it is to achieve higher management efficiency and robustness at a lower computational cost. By collecting more comprehensive data on load operating conditions, introducing advanced

prediction models and algorithms, and further considering the different operating styles of load operators in the prediction process (Hu, 2021), it is possible to make more accurate predictions of the future operating conditions that HESS needs to handle, thereby reducing uncertainty and improving the efficiency and robustness of HESS energy management. Thus, integrating effective prediction models with existing energy management methods, while ensuring the computational complexity meets practical requirements, is a pressing issue to be solved.

2. For energy management methods based on optimization and condition pattern recognition that rely on dynamic response models and aging models of HESS, the accuracy of the models they are based on directly impacts the final energy management effectiveness. Currently, there is a problem where the models used in related energy management methods tend to be overly simple and do not closely align with the actual operating conditions of HESS. These methods often fail to accurately reflect the voltage, current responses, and aging conditions of HESS under special conditions such as low temperatures or high discharge rates. Therefore, a crucial issue is how to accurately model the HESS system based on its actual operating conditions and environment to support energy management methods.

3. Real-time power distribution control is required during HESS operation, which places high demands on the real-time performance of energy management methods during online application. In existing research, energy management methods with high online computational complexity, such as model predictive control and condition pattern recognition, often struggle to meet real-time requirements in practical use. These methods may fail to provide timely power distribution reference values to the controller or may not update energy management strategies in time, directly affecting the management efficiency and robustness of these methods. Some researchers have already conducted preliminary explorations combining model predictive control or machine learning-based energy management methods with cloud computing (Hou, 2020), but there is still significant room for further exploration in enhancing the real-time performance of energy management methods through cloud collaboration, thus improving their management efficiency and robustness.

In addition, most existing research on HESS energy management focuses on electric vehicle HESS (Mali, 2021), with only a few studies addressing hybrid storage power sources for other transportation vehicles, such as light rail and ships, and HESS in applications like grid energy storage (Veerendra, 2024). While advanced results for energy management of electric vehicle HESS continue to emerge, further research is needed to develop energy management methods for HESS designed for other types of load conditions and operating environments.

Conclusion

This article first briefly introduces the controlled and uncontrolled topologies of LIB/SC hybrid energy storage systems, analyses the connection methods and main characteristics of active, semi-active, and passive topologies, and provides an overview of the functional architecture and power allocation control process of the LIB/SC hybrid energy storage system EMS. It then emphasizes four categories of energy management methods for LIB/SC hybrid energy storage systems: experience-based, optimization-based, working condition pattern recognition-based, and machine learning-based methods. The specific processes and performance characteristics of each energy management method are classified, detailed, and compared. Finally, the performance characteristics of existing energy management methods, regarding management efficiency, robustness, and computational complexity, are summarized, and future research directions and development trends for energy management methods in LIB/SC hybrid energy storage systems are discussed.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their sincere gratitude to Dr. Arshad Javad for his invaluable contributions and support throughout this research. His insightful feedback on the energy management methodologies and his assistance in data analysis significantly enhanced the depth and quality of this work. Additionally, we appreciate his dedication to refining the manuscript and guiding the experimental design, which were instrumental in achieving the final results.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

- Abedin, T., Pasupuleti, J., Paw, J. K. S., Tak, Y. C., Mahmud, M., Abdullah, M. P., & Nur-E-Alam, M. (2025). Proton exchange membrane fuel cells in electric vehicles: Innovations, challenges, and pathways to sustainability. *Journal of Power Sources*, 640, 236769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.236769>
- Baker, J. (2008). New technology and possible advances in energy storage. *Energy Policy*, 36(12), 4368-4373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2008.09.040>
- Cheng, L., Zhang, F., Liu, S., & Zhang, Z. (2020). Configuration method of hybrid energy storage system for high power density in More Electric Aircraft. *Journal of power sources*, 445, 227322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.227322>
- Gopi, C. V. M., & Ramesh, R. (2024). Review of battery-supercapacitor hybrid energy storage systems for electric vehicles. *Results in Engineering*, 103598. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.103598>
- Hasan, M. M., Haque, R., Jahirul, M. I., Rasul, M. G., Fattah, I. M. R., Hassan, N. M. S., & Mofijur, M. (2025). Advancing energy storage: The future trajectory of lithium-ion battery technologies. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 120, 116511. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.116511>
- Hong, J., Liang, F., & Yang, H. (2023). Research progress, trends and prospects of big data technology for new energy power and energy storage system. *Energy Reviews*, 2(3), 100036. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enrev.2023.100036>
- Hou, J., & Song, Z. (2020). A hierarchical energy management strategy for hybrid energy storage via vehicle-to-cloud connectivity. *Applied energy*, 257, 113900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113900>
- Hu, J., Liu, D., Du, C., Yan, F., & Lv, C. (2020). Intelligent energy management strategy of hybrid energy storage system for electric vehicle based on driving pattern recognition. *Energy*, 198, 117298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.117298>
- Hu, L., Zhou, X., Zhang, X., Wang, F., Li, Q., & Wu, W. (2021). A review on key challenges in intelligent vehicles: Safety and driver-oriented features. *IET Intelligent Transport Systems*, 15(9), 1093-1105. <https://doi.org/10.1049/itr2.12088>
- Jiang, H., Zhao, Y., & Ma, S. (2025). Dual-Layer Energy Management Strategy for a Hybrid Energy Storage System to Enhance PHEV Performance. *Energies*, 18(7), 1667. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18071667>

- Kouchachvili, L., Yaïci, W., & Entchev, E. (2018). Hybrid battery/supercapacitor energy storage system for the electric vehicles. *Journal of Power Sources*, 374, 237-248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.11.040>
- Kumaresan, N., & Rammohan, A. (2024). A comprehensive review on energy management strategies of hybrid energy storage systems for electric vehicles. *Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering*, 46(3), 146. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40430-024-04736-x>
- LI, H., CHU, J., SUN, S., & LI, H. (2021). Characteristics of vehicle-mounted electromagnetic coupling flywheel energy storage system. *Energy Storage Science and Technology*, 10(5), 1687. <https://doi.org/10.19799/j.cnki.2095-4239.2021.0318>
- Li, W., & Joos, G. (2008, June). A power electronic interface for a battery supercapacitor hybrid energy storage system for wind applications. In 2008 IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference (pp. 1762-1768). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/PESC.2008.4592198>
- Mali, V., & Tripathi, B. (2021). Thermal and economic analysis of hybrid energy storage system based on lithium-ion battery and supercapacitor for electric vehicle application. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 23, 1135-1150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-020-01824-z>
- Mallon, K., & Assadian, F. (2022). A study of control methodologies for the trade-off between battery aging and energy consumption on electric vehicles with hybrid energy storage systems. *Energies*, 15(2), 600. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15020600>
- Manikandan, M., Anto Feradrick Samson, V., Manikandan, E., Karthigeyan, K. A., & Papanasam, E. (2025). A Comprehensive Review on Materials Research Progress and Applications of Photo-Supercapacitors. *Journal of Electronic Materials*, 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11664-025-11981-w>
- Niaz, A., Kader, M. S., Khan, S., Shoukat, M. U., Nawaz, S. A., Niaz, F., & Niaz, I. (2023). Environment Friendly Hybrid Solar-Hydro Power Distribution Scheduling on Demand Side. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*, 32(1). <https://doi.org/10.15244/pjoes/152810>
- Petrovic, S., & Petrovic, S. (2021). Nickel–cadmium batteries. *Battery Technology Crash Course: A Concise Introduction*, 73-88. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57269-3_4
- Ramu, S. K., Vairavasundaram, I., Palaniyappan, B., Bragadeshwaran, A., & Aljafari, B. (2024). Enhanced energy management of DC microgrid: Artificial neural networks-driven hybrid energy storage system with integration of bidirectional DC-DC converter. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 88, 111562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.111562>
- Reber, D. (2025). Electrolyte tank costs are an overlooked factor in flow battery economics. *Nature Energy*, 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-024-01677-6>
- Reddy, K. J., & Natarajan, S. (2018). Energy sources and multi-input DC-DC converters used in hybrid electric vehicle applications—A review. *International journal of hydrogen energy*, 43(36), 17387-17408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.07.076>
- Ren, G., Ma, G., & Cong, N. (2015). Review of electrical energy storage system for vehicular applications. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 41, 225-236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.08.003>
- Ruan, J., Walker, P. D., Zhang, N., & Wu, J. (2017). An investigation of hybrid energy storage system in multi-speed electric vehicle. *Energy*, 140, 291-306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.08.119>
- Shafiei, K., Seifi, A., & Hagh, M. T. (2025). A novel multi-objective optimization approach for resilience enhancement considering integrated energy systems with renewable energy, energy storage, energy

- sharing, and demand-side management. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 115, 115966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.115966>
- Shen, K., Xu, W., Lai, X., Li, D., Meng, X., Zheng, Y., & Feng, X. (2025). Physics-informed machine learning estimation of the temperature of large-format lithium-ion batteries under various operating conditions. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 269, 126200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2025.126200>
- Shoukat, M. U., Yan, L., Du, C., Raza, M. U. M., Adeel, M., & Khan, T. (2022, October). Application of digital twin in smart battery electric vehicle: Industry 4.0. In *2022 International conference on IT and industrial technologies (ICIT)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIT56493.2022.9989044>
- Shu, L., & Rui, L. (2020, August). Power allocation control method for hybrid energy storage system of lithium ion battery and supercapacitor. In *2020 Chinese Control And Decision Conference (CCDC)* (pp. 1346-1350). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCDC49329.2020.9164804>
- Song, Z., Hofmann, H., Li, J., Han, X., Zhang, X., & Ouyang, M. (2015). A comparison study of different semi-active hybrid energy storage system topologies for electric vehicles. *Journal of Power Sources*, 274, 400-411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.10.061>
- Takvi-Aninakwa, P., Wang, S., Liu, G., Fernandez, C., Kang, W., & Song, Y. (2025). Deep learning framework designed for high-performance lithium-ion batteries state monitoring. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 218, 115803. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.115803>
- Tong, Y., Salhi, I., Wang, Q., Lu, G., & Wu, S. (2025). Bidirectional DC-DC Converter Topologies for Hybrid Energy Storage Systems in Electric Vehicles: A Comprehensive Review. *Energies*, 18(9), 2312. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en18092312>
- Vanlalchhuanawmi, C., Deb, S., Onen, A., & Ustun, T. S. (2024). Energy management strategies in distribution system integrating electric vehicle and battery energy storage system: A review. *Energy Storage*, 6(5), e682. <https://doi.org/10.1002/est2.682>
- Veerendra, A. S., Mohamed, M. R. B., & García Márquez, F. P. (2024). Energy management control strategies for energy storage systems of hybrid electric vehicle: A review. *Energy Storage*, 6(1), e573. <https://doi.org/10.1002/est2.573>
- Wang, Y., Zhang, X., Liu, C., Pan, R., & Chen, Z. (2018). Multi-timescale power and energy assessment of lithium-ion battery and supercapacitor hybrid system using extended Kalman filter. *Journal of Power Sources*, 389, 93-105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2018.04.012>
- Wu, J., Li, S., Lan, Y., Chen, S., Li, Z., & Li, Z. (2025). Research progress on 3D printed flexible supercapacitors based on nanomaterial inks. *Journal of Energy Storage*, 118, 116140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.116140>
- Xiong, R., Chen, H., Wang, C., & Sun, F. (2018). Towards a smarter hybrid energy storage system based on battery and ultracapacitor-A critical review on topology and energy management. *Journal of cleaner production*, 202, 1228-1240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.08.134>
- Yanamandra, K., Pinisetty, D., Daoud, A., & Gupta, N. (2022). Recycling of Li-ion and lead acid batteries: a review. *Journal of the Indian Institute of Science*, 102(1), 281-295. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41745-021-00269-7>
- Youfeng, Z., Quancai, X., & Peizhuang, Z. (2025). Vibration Suppression of Vehicle Dual rotor Flywheel Battery Based on Nonlinear Energy Sink. *Iranian Journal of Science and Technology, Transactions of Mechanical Engineering*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40997-025-00865-3>

